

THE ROLE OF COMMUNICATION PROCESS MANAGEMENT IN PROJECT SUCCESS: BEST PRACTICES AND CASE STUDIES WITH REFERENCE TO HARSHA TOYOTA

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ABSTRACT

When compared to the more conventional methods of management communication, such as face-to-face (FTF), telephone, and written note, managers may find that computer-based options are more beneficial. In this study, researchers looked at how continuing management groups that were working together used electronic messaging (EM). Using a comprehensive multimethod case study of two daily newspapers' editorial groups, it looked at how well the selected communication medium (FTF vs. EM) aligned with the intended form of discourse (alternation vs. interaction/discussion). This preliminary investigation led to the formulation of two hypotheses. The first maintains that CMC is more suited for communicating within an existing context, while FTF is more suited to constructing a common interpretative framework among group members due to its high degree of interactivity. For interactive conversation, groups who are good at communicating will employ FTF, while for discourse that mostly consists of alternating adjacency pairs, they will use EM. In the second, it is suggested that communication may be made more successful by selecting the right ways of expression.

The four core characteristics of management that Warren Bennis identified—attention, meaning, trust, and self—all revolve on communication. Managers and leaders who want to make a difference in their organizations need to work on being more self-aware, setting a good example when it comes to communication, and mastering the art of constructive disagreement. Assisting managers and executives in improving their communication skills is a critical component of any communication professional's job description.

The emphasis of this study is on the interaction between IT staff and supervisors at a Greek bank as it pertains to the dissemination of risk messaging across different types of organizations. Modern e-banking security managers rely heavily on communication tools to accomplish an essential part of information systems (IS) security: protecting the architecture of the system.

I. INTRODUCTION

Communication is a process whereby information is enclosed in a package and is channeled and imparted by a sender to a receiver via some medium. The receiver then decodes the message and gives the sender a feedback. All forms of communication require a sender, a message, and an intended recipient, however the receiver need not be present or aware of the sender's intent to communicate at the time of

communication in order for the act of communication to occur. Communication requires that all parties have an area of communicative commonality. There are verbal means using language and there are nonverbal means, such as body language, sign language, paralanguage, haptic communication, chronemics, and eye contact, through media, i.e., pictures, graphics and sound, and writing.

Information communication revolutions

Over time, technology has progressed and has created new forms of and ideas about communication. The newer advances include media and communications psychology. Media psychology is an emerging field of study. These technological advances revolutionized the processes of communication. Researchers have divided how communication was transformed into three revolutionary stages:

In the 1st Information Communication Revolution, the first written communication began, with pictographs. These writings were made on stone, which were too heavy to transfer. During this era, written communication was not mobile, but nonetheless existed.

In the 2nd Information Communication Revolution, writing began to appear on paper, papyrus, clay, wax, etc. Common alphabets were introduced, allowing the uniformity of language across large distances. Much later the Gutenberg printing-press was invented. Gutenberg created this printing-press after a long period of time in the 15th century.

In the 3rd Information Communication Revolution, information can now be transferred via controlled waves and electronic signals.

Communication is thus a process by which meaning is assigned and conveyed in an attempt to create shared understanding. This process requires a vast repertoire of skills in interpersonal processing, listening, observing, speaking, questioning, analyzing, gestures and evaluating. It is through communication that collaboration and cooperation occur.

There are also many common barriers to successful communication, two of which are **message overload** (when a person receives too many messages at the same time), and **message complexity**. Communication is a continuous process. The psychology of media communications is an emerging area of increasing attention and study.

II. NEED & IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY:

The need of the Communication Process as management is to determine what aspects of performance are required to be evaluated.

- To identify those who are performing their assigned task well and those who are not and the reason for such performance.

- To provide information about the Communication Process as management basing on which decisions regarded conformation, promotion, demotion and transfer are taken.
- To provide feedback information about the level of achievements and behavior of an employee.
- To provide information and counsel the employee.
- To compare actual performance with the standards and in out deviations (positive and negative)
- To create and maintain satisfactory level of performance.
- To prevent grievance and in disciplinary activity.
- To facilitate fair and equitable compensation.
- To ensure organizational effectiveness.
- It guarantees useful information about employees and the nature of their duties.

We can briefly say that Communication Process as management systems are necessities to assess performance at regular intervals with consistency to study improvements, deviation and to take corrective actions to bride gaps and improve performance over a period of time.

III. OBJECTIVES:

The objective is to know how effective is the execution of Communication Process as management in TOYOTA, Hyderabad.

The aim of Communication Process as management is to encourage the employees to set his own objective for the next time period following the review of his past performance. It enables the management to make effective decisions/ to modify earlier decisions based on the evaluation of the existing plans, information system, job analysis, and internal and external environment factors influencing employee performance.

The objectives is to identify the common goals of the organization, define each individuals major areas of responsibility in terms results expected of him, review the individual performance progress in a job and his potential for future improvement. It aims at providing data to managers with whom they may judge future job assignments and compensation.

To counsel the employees Communication Process regarding their strengths and weaknesses and asses in developing them to realize they are full potential in line with the company's objectives and goals. Always emphasize that the role of a manager is to offer constructive support and not condemn. Give the employees many opportunities to ask guidance to air grievances and discuss anxieties

IV. SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

In the present study an attempt has been made to know the actual implementation of Communication Process as management techniques in general and some other aspects such as awareness of the workers, effectiveness of the performance appraisal system in particular.

Human resource projections are valid on appraisals. By improving job skills, the employees have lot of scope for development and prepare themselves for higher responsibilities.

A through analysis of the performance appraisal system will help the management to know the short comings, if any. It also help the company in knowing whether the performance appraisal techniques are used to full extent or not, there by the researcher can understand the effective implement of the performance appraisal system.

V. METHODOLOGY & DATABASE:

The research methodology is a systematic way to solve the problem and it is an important component of the study without which researcher may not be able to obtain the facts and figures from the employees.

SOURCE OF DATA:

The study is based on primary as well as secondary data collected from different sources:

A). Primary Data:

The primary data is collected with the help of questionnaires, which consists of twenty questions each. The questionnaires are chosen because of its simplicity and liability. Researcher can expect straight answers to the questions. The respondents are informed about the significant of the study and requested to give their fair opinions.

B). Secondary Data:

Secondary data is collected through the documents provided by the personnel department. The documents include personnel manuals, books, reports, journal, etc.

SAMPLING PROCESS:

A). Sample Unit:

The executives and employed at TOYOTA. Hyderabad constitute 'universe' of the present study. A part of it is taken as sample unit for the resent study. It includes JGMS, AGMS, manager and other employees of TOYOTA Hyderabad.

B). Sample Size:

The sample size consists of 100 respondents employed in TOYOTA, Hyderabad. Of these 30 are executives, 20 are senior executives and the remaining 50 are employees.

PERIOD OF THE STUDY:

Since so many years TOYOTA Hyderabad has been following the same procedure of Communication Process for their executives and employees and for the study of my project last one-year data has collected on performance appraisals.

VI. LIMITATIONS

1. Firstly the respondents were not available readily and the data were collected as per the convenience of the respondents.
2. Secondly the sample of respondents was very less given by the organization hence appropriate sample technique was not applied for selecting the respondents.
3. Thirdly, time is also one of constraints. Duration of 45 days is not sufficient to cover all the aspects of the study.

For the above limitation the study conducted may not give the true representation of the entire organization.

THE PROCESS OF COMMUNICATION

As such there are three steps involved in the communication process. It is the origin of a thought or an idea by a sender which is properly planned and then passed on to the receiver in a manner in which it can be properly understood.

The Communication Process.

- **The message sender**

Communication begins when the sender comes across a thought or an idea. The sender then encodes it in a way in which it can be understood by the receiving channel members. Encoding is not simply

translation or to put forward an idea, but includes additions, deletions and simplifications in the line of thought and conversion and the same in the form of a message to be transferred further down the line. It also may include technical details such as encoding the message in a programmed language as an input for computer.

- **Transmission of Message**

There needs to be a link between the sender of the message and receiver of the message. These links or mediums may be written or oral. The messages are transmitted through a letter, a telegram, telephone, computer, etc. Sometimes, more than one link also may be used for the transmission of messages.

The message receiver

The message has to reach the receiver in a form in which it is understandable. The message received has to be decoded. It is to be converted into the original thought or idea. Accurate communication can occur only when both, the sender and the receiver attach similar meanings to the symbols that compose the message. The crux is in the message being understood. The emphasis is not simply in the transfer of the message but such a transfer where facts remain intact and the real message does not get distorted. It is necessary to receive a message with an open mind because if the information is contrary to the value system of the individual, a closed mind will normally not accept it.

To verify the effectiveness of communication, feedback is necessary. Whether or not a message has been clearly transmitted and understood can be confirmed by feedback. Feedback helps in analyzing whether the objective has been achieved or not.

Communication modeling

Shannon and Weaver Model of Communication

Communication major dimensions scheme

The first major model for communication came in 1949 by Claude Shannon and Warren Weaver for Bell Laboratories. The original model was designed to mirror the functioning of radio and telephone technologies. Their initial model consisted of three primary parts: sender, channel, and receiver. The sender was the part of a telephone a person spoke into, the channel was the telephone itself, and the receiver was the part of the phone where one could hear the other person. Shannon and Weaver also recognized that often there is static that interferes with one listening to a telephone conversation, which they deemed noise.

In a simple model, often referred to as the transmission model or standard view of communication, information or content (e.g. a message in natural language) is sent in some form (as spoken language) from an emisor/ sender/ encoder to a destination/ receiver/ decoder. This common conception of communication simply views communication as a means of sending and receiving information. The strengths of this model are simplicity, generality, and quantifiability. Social scientists Claude Shannon and Warren Weaver structured this model based on the following elements:

1. An information source, which produces a message.
2. A transmitter, which encodes the message into signals
3. A channel, to which signals are adapted for transmission
4. A receiver, which 'decodes' (reconstructs) the message from the signal.
5. A destination, where the message arrives.

Shannon and Weaver argued that there were three levels of problems for communication within this theory.

1. The technical problem: how accurately can the message be transmitted?
2. The semantic problem: how precisely is the meaning 'conveyed'?
3. The effectiveness problem: how effectively does the received meaning affect behavior?

Daniel Chandler critiques the transmission model by stating

- It assumes communicators are isolated individuals.
- No allowance for differing purposes.
- No allowance for differing interpretations.
- No allowance for unequal power relations.
- No allowance for situational contexts.

Communication noise

In any communication model, noise is interference with the decoding of messages sent over a channel by an encoder. There are many examples of noise:

Environmental Noise: Noise that physically disrupts communication, such as standing next to loud speakers at a party, or the noise from a construction site next to a classroom making it difficult to hear the professor.

Physiological-Impairment Noise: Physical maladies that prevent effective communication, such as actual deafness or blindness preventing messages from being received as they were intended.

Semantic Noise: Different interpretations of the meanings of certain words. For example, the word "weed" can be interpreted as an undesirable plant in your yard, or as a euphemism for marijuana.

Syntactical Noise: Mistakes in grammar can disrupt communication, such as abrupt changes in verb tense during a sentence.

Organizational Noise: Poorly structured communication can prevent the receiver from accurate interpretation. For example, unclear and badly stated directions can make the receiver even more lost.

Cultural Noise: Stereotypical assumptions can cause misunderstandings, such as unintentionally offending a non-Christian person by wishing them a "Merry Christmas."

Psychological Noise: Certain attitudes can also make communication difficult. For instance, great anger or sadness may cause someone to lose focus on the present moment. Disorders such as Autism may also severely hamper effective communication.

Communication as academic discipline

Communication as an academic discipline, sometimes called "communicology," relates to all the ways we communicate, so it embraces a large body of study and knowledge. The communication discipline includes both verbal and nonverbal messages. A body of scholarship all about communication is presented and explained in textbooks, electronic publications, and academic journals. In the journals,

researchers report the results of studies that are the basis for an ever-expanding understanding of how we all communicate.

Communication happens at many levels (even for one single action), in many different ways, and for most beings, as well as certain machines. Several, if not all, fields of study dedicate a portion of attention to communication, so when speaking about communication it is very important to be sure about what aspects of communication one is speaking about. Definitions of communication range widely, some recognizing that animals can communicate with each other as well as human beings, and some are more narrow, only including human beings within the different parameters of human symbolic interaction.

Communication theory

Human communication is understood in various ways by those who identify with the field. This diversity is the result of communication being a relatively young field of study, composed of a very broad constituency of disciplines. It includes work taken from scholars of Rhetoric, Journalism, Sociology, Psychology, Anthropology, and Semiotics, among others. Cognate areas include biocommunication, which investigates communicative processes within and among non-humans such as bacteria, animals, fungi and plants, and information theory, which provides a mathematical model for measuring communication within and among systems.

Generally, human communication is concerned with the making of meaning and the exchange of understanding. One model of communication considers it from the perspective of transmitting information from one person to another. In fact, many scholars of communication take this as a working definition, and use Lasswell's maxim, "who says what to whom in what channel with what effect," as a means of circumscribing the field of **communication theory**. Among those who subscribe to the transmission model are those who identify themselves with the communication sciences, and finds its roots in the studies of propaganda and mass media of the early 20th century.

A simple communication model with a sender transferring a message containing information to a receiver.

Other commentators claim that a ritual process of communication exists, one not artificially divorcible from a particular historical and social context. This tradition is largely associated with early scholars of symbolic interactionism as well as phenomenologists.

Constructionist Models

There is an additional working definition of communication to consider that authors like Richard A. Lanham (2003) and as far back as Erving Goffman (1959) have highlighted. This is a progression from Lasswell's attempt to define human communication through to this century and revolutionized into the constructionist model. Constructionists believe that the process of communication is in itself the only messages that exist. The packaging can not be separated from the social and historical context from which it arose, therefore the substance to look at in communication theory is style for Richard Lanham and the performance of self for Erving Goffman.

Lanham chose to view communication as the rival to the over encompassing use of CBS model (which pursued to further the transmission model). CBS model argues that clarity, brevity, and sincerity are the only purpose to prose discourse, therefore communication. Lanham wrote, "If words matter too, if the whole range of human motive is seen as animating prose discourse, then rhetoric analysis leads us to the essential questions about prose style" (Lanham 10). This is saying that rhetoric and style are fundamentally important; they are not errors to what we actually intend to transmit. The process which we construct and deconstruct meaning deserves analysis.

Erving Goffman sees the performance of self as the most important frame to understand communication. Goffman wrote, "What does seem to be required of the individual is that he learn enough pieces of expression to be able to 'fill in' and manage, more or less, any part that he is likely to be given" (Goffman 73) Goffman is highlighting the significance of expression. The truth in both cases is the articulation of the message and the package as one. The construction of the message from social and historical context is the seed as is the pre-existing message is for the transmission model. Therefore any look into communication theory should include the possibilities drafted by such great scholars as Richard A. Lanham and Erving Goffman that style and performance is the whole process.

Communication stands so deeply rooted in human behaviors and the structures of society that scholars have difficulty thinking of it while excluding social or behavioral events. Because communication theory remains a relatively young field of inquiry and integrates itself with other disciplines such as philosophy, psychology, and sociology, one probably cannot yet expect a consensus conceptualization of communication across disciplines.

VII. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

1. Do you think Communication Process management is needed in a company?

(a) YES

(b) NO

s.no	Options	No. of Responses	Percentage
1	YES	100	100
2	NO	0	0
	TOTAL	100	100

Interpretation:

To above question, almost 100% of the employees thought that the Communication Process management is needed in a company.

2. Communication Process management rating is used to

- (a) Identify areas of improvement
- (b) Identifying quality for unit of work
- (c) Set performance target
- (d) All the above

s.no	Options	No. of Responses	Percentage
1	Identify areas of improvement	28	28
2	Identify areas of training & development	48	48
3	Set performance target	8	8
4	All the above	16	16
	Total	100	100

Interpretation:

About the usefulness of Communication Process management, 28% have said that appraisal system helped them to identify areas of improvement, to 48% it helped in identifying training & development needs, to 8% it helped in setting performance targets and to 16% it was helpful in all the above areas. By this we can say that P.A is helpful in one way or the other for the employees.

3. In your experience the outstanding Communication management of an employee is due to:

- (a) Actual Performance
- (b) Qualification
- (c) Experience
- (d) All the above

s.no	Options	No. of Responses	Percentage
1	Actual Performance	28	28
2	Qualification	0	0
3	Experience	52	52
4	All the above	20	20
	total	100	100

Interpretation:

Above 28% of the employees responded that the outstanding Performance appraisal is due to Actual Performance, 52% of the employees is due to Experience and 20% of the employees is due to all the above.

VIII. FINDINGS

1. In the light of the above discussion the following findings and conclusions are Made.
 1. It is revealed that the executive are getting feedback on their Communication Process though which they can review their performance. Sort on the problems and can overcome the difficulties.
 2. The management has a clear understanding about the problem that the workers are the best with moreover, they are eager to solve the problems of the workers as and when they arise.
 3. The management was giving requisite training in Communication to workers in the areas where they are weak.

4. Workers awareness about the fact that Communication Process is one of the factors for promotion was cent percent.
5. Communication Process system is considered as a means that aim at identifying the areas of improvement, identifying areas of training and development setting performance target for future.
6. The management desire having cordial relations with the work to hold mutual discussions.
7. The Communication Process system it exists as it exists now is properly worked out and appropriately evolved. This revealed from the opinion given by the majority of the employees.

IX. SUGGESTIONS

- The company should maintain their market position and try to increase their customers.
- Enough stock should keep in stockiest place& retailers place
- To enable the customers to get in touch with the service personal more easily, the number of direct phones should be increase or provide the toll free number to give solutions of constructions.
- Periodically, review meetings with the customers in different areas should be convinced, to have a general consensus regarding problems being faced by them.
- The respondents are paying their bills at the company show rooms, and these are also acting as customer care centers for all queries and needs of the consumers.
- The service is also well received by the respondents and they are satisfied with quality and price, moreover it is largely used by people who are offering public cell office facilities.
- The instruments being providing with fixed line service are being well received by the respondents.

X. CONCLUSION

The following are some ideas and recommendations based on the study's results and in-depth interviews with TOYOTA. Hyderabad executives and employees:

- Notifying staff right away is highly encouraged.
- Even more so when the evaluation comes back negative.
- It's best practice for a supervisor to assess an employee's strengths and areas for improvement, and then provide guidance on how to address the employee's deficiencies.
- Properly advising workers on their strengths and areas for improvement and helping them grow into their maximum potential in accordance with the company's objectives is highly recommended.
- Keeping the Communication Process system in its current form is a major priority for upper management. In order to foster amicable interactions and mutual understanding between upper management and executives, the Communication Process system is seen as a crucial instrument.
- It is advised that workers be informed about their performance, given the opportunity to respond, and, if needed, be given guidance on how to improve in the future.
- It is expected that the rater has extensive knowledge of the rating system's philosophy. It is essential to identify, evaluate, and explain factor sales in great detail.

Finally, in order to fortify the system, it is essential to eliminate any potential obstacles.

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